

Integrated germplasm improvement

Yield potential of irrigated IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan V at Ndop Plain

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Rice, a relatively new crop in Cameroon, is grown on about 20,000 ha of irrigated land. Ndop Plain, one of three major rice production areas, is situated at 1,200 m above sea level. Irrigated rice is grown on an estimated 3,000 ha; a further 15,000 ha is potentially suitable for rice cultivation. The major constraints to increased rice production are low temperatures during the growing season and associated problems of diseases such as sheath rot (ShR) and grain discoloration (Gd).

Tainan V is still being grown by some farmers because of its good taste. But its poor grain quality (bold, short, chalky grain, and poor keeping quality) does not compete with imported rice in the open market. In 1987, IR7167-33-2-3 was released for general cultivation. It has superior grain quality (medium-long, less chalky, and fair keeping quality), yield, cold tolerance, and resistance to ShR and Gd.

We collected data over several seasons of experiment station and farmers' field trials to compare yields. In experiment station yield trials, early transplanting, 25- × 20-cm spacing, and rate of 2-3 seedlings/hill were practiced. Fertilizers were applied at 60-17.6-33 kg NPK/ha. In farmers' field trials, nursery, transplanting, and crop management were according to normal practices and calendar.

Table 1 shows results of 1987 and 1988 yield trials at Bamunka research site. In 1987, Tainan V yields ranged from 3.2 to 5.0 t/ha; IR7167-33-2-3 yields ranged from 4.9 to 6.3 t/ha. The highest yielding plot of Tainan V achieved 80% of the yield of IR7167-33-2-3 in the same trial and 91% of the mean of IR7167-33-2-3. In 1988 experiment station trials, IR7167-33-2-3 outyielded Tainan V by an average 36%. Tainan V yielded 2.7-3.7 t/ha, IR7167-33-2-3 4.3-5.5 t/ha.

IR7167-33-2-3 also showed greater resistance to ShR and Gd.

Table 2 shows results from farmers' field trials in the Bamunka farm area. In 1987, IR7167-33-2-3 outyielded Tainan V on all six farms sampled, by margins of 28-65%. Yields of Tainan V ranged from 2.7 to 5.4 t/ha, IR7167-33-2-3 from 3.4 to 6.3 t/ha. Yields in 1988 were similar.

IR7167-33-2-3 has an average yield advantage over Tainan V of about 32% at Bamunka farm and 45% in farmers' fields. Its performance was consistent over 2 yr. □

Table 2. Yields of IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan V in farmers' fields at Ndop Plain, Cameroon, 1987-88.

Variety or line	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	
	1987	1988
Tainan V	3.4	3.2
IR7167-33-2-3	4.9	4.5

^aMean of 6 farms sampled each year.

Table 1. Performance of IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan V in experiment station yield trials. Ndop Plain, Bamunka, Cameroon, 1987-88.

Variety or line	Yield ^a (t/ha)		Duration (d)	Reaction ^b to		Panicle exsertion ^b (0-9)
	1987	1988		Sheath rot (0-9)	Grain discoloration (0-9)	
IR7167-33-2-3	5.5	4.4	142	3	3	3

^aMean of 6 trials each year. ^bStandard evaluation system for rice.

ITA173, a high-yielding rice variety for irrigated areas in Tanzania

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We tested a number of entries from IRTP nurseries at DRC under irrigated condition in the 1983 wet season. ITA173 was identified as promising and was tested in observation and preliminary yield trials in 1983 and

Yield performance of ITA173 in trials at 4 locations in Tanzania, 1985-87 dry and wet seasons.

Year and season	Location and region	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		ITA173	Local check
1985 Wet	Dakawa RC-Morogoro	4.7	2.5 (Katrin)
1985 Wet	Dakawa RC-Morogoro	7.7	4.3 (IR579)
1985 Wet	Dakawa RC-Morogoro	7.6	4.9 (Katrin)
1985 Dry	Dakawa RC-Morogoro	4.4	3.3 (Katrin)
1986 Wet	Dakawa RC-Morogoro	7.1	4.5 (Supa)
1986 Wet	DRF Farms-Morogoro	4.3	3.9 (IR8)
1986 Wet	Igurusi-Mbeya	6.1	3.8 (Kihogo)
1986 Wet	Mwamapuli Igunga-Tabora	4.4	2.4 (Supa)
1986 Dry	DRF Farms-Morogoro	7.0	5.6 (Katrin)
1987 Wet	Dakawa RC-Morogoro	6.8	3.6 (Supa)
1987 Dry	Dry Farms-Morogoro	7.8	5.6 (Katrin)
Mean		6.2	